

Recent Progressions on Peripheral Hypotheses of Hypothalamic Aging

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Abstract

Background: It is well known that the changes of hypothalamus in control of hormones determine the chronological manifestations of aging in mammals.

Aim: It is aimed to review the progressions on recently hypothesized peripheral mechanisms responsible for the senescent changes of the hypothalamic nuclei and secretion.

Methods: It was searched the papers from Pubmed and Baidu, and then analyzed and summarized.

Results and Discussions: (a) It was proposed by Cai that the decrease in slow-wave sleep (SWS) resulting from continual skin aging cause both decrease in secretion of growth hormone (GH) and degeneration of suprachiasmatic nucleus(SCN) for hypothalamus. (b) It was soon hypothesized by the Europeans that the increase in body fat be responsible for the degeneration of male hypothalamic preoptic sexually dimorphic nucleus (SDN-POA), which was supported by the increment of aromatase converting testosterone to estradiol as proposed by Cohen, with testosterone required to maintain SDN-POA. In parallel, it was speculated the aging of female ovary toward menopause as acceleration and precocity similarly in association with the corresponding senescent changes in lipid, aromatase and estradiol. (c) It was the hypothalamic paraventricular nucleus (PVN) that retained neuron number unchanged during aging for psychological stress..

Conclusion: It is summarized that the hypothalamic senescence resulting from these peripheral mechanisms shifts the functional balance among these three hypothalamic systems toward aging.

Introduction

Among the various senescent mechanisms, the changes of hypothalamic neuroendocrine in control of hormones [1,2] determine the chronological sequence of aging in the ontogenetic life of vertebrates including mammals.

Aging researches decades of years ago revealed that the hypothalamic nuclei manifested heterogeneity in degeneration during aging in mammals [1,3,4,5,6]. The paraventricular nucleus (PVN) was responsible for stress response and was functional throughout the lifespan, maintaining its neuron number in senescence in humans [1,3]. In contrast, the suprachiasmatic nucleus (SCN), the main controller of circadian rhythm, was decreased in its number of neurons during the aging process in humans and marmosets [1,3,5]. Moreover, the sexually dimorphic nucleus in preoptic area (SDN-POA) declined sharply in cell number after aging in male humans and rats[1,3,4,6]. All these

manifestations demonstrated the heterogeneity of hypothalamic nuclei during the complex degenerative processes of aging.

Besides the structural changes in hypothalamic nuclei, there also occurs the changes in hypothalamic secretion of hormones, most notably as the growth hormone (GH)[7,8,9], sex hormones[10,11], and so on. In this article, it is attempted to review the progressions on recently proposed important hypotheses regarding the peripheral mechanisms causing all these hypothalamic changes during aging.

Methods

To deal with such an important but complicated theme, there was no better and more convincing way than integrative review of all related fields of researches. Meta-analysis fit investigation of a specific topic in a well-studied subfield, while neglected many discussions in various review papers. Besides, many newly proposed hypotheses provided only one or two

More Information

How to cite this article: Cai Z-J. Recent Progressions on Peripheral Hypotheses of Hypothalamic Aging. Eur J Med Health Res, 2024;2(5):256-61.

DOI: 10.59324/ejmhr.2024.2(5).26

Keywords:

Aging,
Slow wave sleep,
Growth hormone,
Sex hormone,
Hypothalamus.

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papers, insufficient for meta-analysis. Thus, meta-analysis did not fit the complicated studies in this paper. Besides, it was certainly required to analyze and integrate the collected hypotheses, reviews and papers from several fields by classification, comparison and summarization.

Papers were searched out from Pubmed and Baidu Xueshu. The updated relevant reviews in subfields were given priority to cite. If not available, relevant reviews were cited. If still unavailable, the salient and repeated experimental results of original articles in subfields were cited. In this way, it was feasible to classify, compare and summarize them to carry out integrative review.

The words and phrases utilized in the search of paper were collected as the followings: “aging”, “slow wave sleep”, “hypothalamus”, “growth hormone”, “aromatase”, “testosterone”, and so on. Sometimes, two or three of these words and phrases were utilized together to restrict the results in search, such as “growth hormone slow wave sleep”, “slow wave sleep aging”, “aromatase aging”, and so on.

Results

The Hypothetic Aging Pathway from Skin to Hypothalamus via Slow Wave Sleep (SWS)

Cai recently suggested a new peripheral hypothesis on reduction in slow wave sleep (SWS) to explain the hypothalamic aging regarding both decrease in secretion of GH [12] and degeneration of SCN [13]. For demonstration, the skin underwent aging from exposure to the environmental sunshine [14,15] and oxygen[16,17] as well as from genetic shortening of the telomere[18,19]. In turn, the skin senescence was

repeatedly reported to result in reduction in the electrodermal activities [12,13,20,21], which would reduce the intensity of emotional responses and memories in brain [22,23,24], and would in turn reduce the requirement for SWS to adjust the less-disrupted emotional balance by accumulation of reduced emotional memories [12,13,25,26,27], as manifested in many senescent observations for the continuous decrement in duration of SWS[28,29,30]. In further, the regulation of SWS on GH secretion was predominant in man [12], because GH secretion in man occurred only in SWS and declined toward aging [7,8,9] along with decrement in duration of SWS [28,29,30]. Accordingly, Cai hypothesized that the decrease in SWS resulting from continual skin aging directly cause the decrease in GH secretion of hypothalamus [12]. In parallel, the reduced requirement for SWS [12,13,25,26,27] would as well decrease the circadian requirement of SCN to inactivate the sympathetic output [31,32], and result in partial degeneration of SCN [12,13].

It is noted that, on the one hand, the senescent decrease in SWS can account for both decrease in secretion of GH [12] and degeneration of SCN [13], while on the other hand in reverse, the co-occurrence of both decrease in secretion of GH [7,8,9,12] and degeneration of SCN [1,3,5,13] in aging indirectly indicates the correctness of this shared mechanism (as reduction in SWS) to explain these two hypothalamic senescent phenomena.

Figure 1 shows the flowchart for the effects from senescent decrement in SWS by continual skin aging to cause both decrease in secretion of GH and degeneration of SCN.

Abbreviation Notes: GH growth hormone; SCN suprachiasmatic nucleus; SWS slow-wave sleep

Figure 1: Flowchart of Senescent Decrement in SWS by Continual Skin Aging to Cause Both Decrease in Secretion of GH and Degeneration of SCN

The Senescent Degeneration of Reproductive System Including Hypothalamus

On July 4, 2016, the European people in television speculated that there was a senescent pathway for male reproduction from the common knowledge of

adipose accumulation and reduction of spermatogenesis in aging to elicit the degeneration of hypothalamic preoptic area(POA) [33,34]. Indeed, it was observed that, by comparing BMI in relation to sperm count, the overweight and obesity were

associated with an increased prevalence of azoospermia or oligozoospermia [35]. In addition, it was repeatedly reported that the male sexually hypothalamic SDN-POA declined in cell number after aging [1,3,4,6]. Furthermore, it was even shown that the higher estradiol could result in the neuronal loss in SDN-POA in male rats [4], while the testosterone reverse the neuronal degeneration within SDN-POA in male Quails [6], demonstrating the reproductive hormonal levels directly able to regulate the neuronal degeneration within the male SDN-POA.

The morphogenetic development and growth in animals is controlled by both induction and termination [36]. Induction initiates the morphogenetic development while termination controls the final shape of the generated organ during development and growth [36]. In mammals, the fat depot sizes reach a peak by middle age or early old age, followed by a substantial decline in advanced old age [37]. Fat tissue growth occurs by increase in size and number of fat cells. Beginning at middle age, the subcutaneous fat loses earlier and consequently the intra-abdominal fat increases relatively in the course toward aging [37].

The enzyme aromatase in vertebrates converts the testosterone to estradiol and decreases the

testosterone levels [38,39]. The aromatase is expressed in the differentiated adipose cells [39]. Accordingly, Cohen suggested that the increase in adipose tissue in middle age be associated with an increase in the enzyme aromatase and lead to diminished testosterone levels during male aging [38].

The disturbance on the male reproductive system from adipose and aromatase by aging can even be assayed *in vivo*. In one report, it was demonstrated that the free and bioavailable estradiol levels decreased modestly with age as did the ratio of free testosterone to free estradiol, the latter testifying to the age-related increase in aromatization of testosterone [40]. The estradiol levels were highly, significantly and positively related to the body fat mass [40].

Accordingly, due to the regulation of neuronal numbers within the hypothalamic SDN-POA by the testosterone and estradiol [4,6], the increment of adipose and aromatase converting the testosterone to estradiol in aging [38,40] would cause the decrement of testosterone and degeneration of neurons within the male SDN-POA. These are the senescent degeneration of male reproductive system.

Abbreviation Notes: SDN-POA hypothalamic sexually dimorphic nucleus in preoptic area; FSH follicle-stimulating hormone

Figure 2: Flowchart for Hormonal Senescence of Reproductive System

The aging of female reproductive system is characterized by the decrease in follicle numbers and decay in oocyte quality [41]. Concurrently, changes in peripheral and hypothalamic endocrinal secretions occur during perimenopause, notably as the increase in estradiol, elevation of follicle-stimulating hormone (FSH) and change in amplitude of pulsatile luteinizing hormone (LH) [10,11]. The increment of adipose and

aromatase converting the testosterone to estradiol in aging [38,39] would likewise cause the increase in female sex hormones [10,11] or decrease in ratio of testosterone/estradiol by aromatase [38,40]. Accordingly, it was speculated that, from the enlightenment of male reproductive aging by sex hormones and recent mechanism of whole ovarian stem cell nests for generation of oocytes [42], the

corresponding increase in the female sex hormones in perimenopause [10,11] might result in acceleration and precocity of oocytes for menopause in mammals [34], in contrast to gradual degeneration of male reproductive system in aging.

Figure 2 shows the flowchart for hormonal senescence of reproductive system.

The Intact Hypothalamic Paraventricular Nucleus (PVN) During Aging

The hypothalamic paraventricular nucleus (PVN), responsible for stress response, is functional throughout the lifespan and maintains its neuron number in aging in humans [1,3]. Obviously, the stress response is thus maintained in aging, which may cause decrease in proteolytic clearance within peripheral cells during aging [43]. Besides, it was recently reviewed that the psychological stress might lead to aging via many other molecular processes in cells, such as the change in length of telomere, increase in DNA damage, alternation in immunological inflammation, and so on [44].

Discussions

Summarized from all of these progressions, it was preliminarily classified by Cai [34] the hypothalamic related aging processes into the followings:

(1) Processes regulated by SCN and growth hormone/insulin-like growth factor 1(GH/IGF1) axis: The reduction of SWS resulting from continual skin aging caused both decrease in GH secretion and degeneration of SCN. This hypothalamic axis primarily controlled the aging of skeletal muscle, stomach, intestine, thymus and brain [34], and secondarily the aging of bone, hypertension, and so on others requiring further investigation [34].

(2) Processes regulated by PVN and hypothalamo-pituitary-adrenal (HPA) axis: This hypothalamic axis was fully functional and maintained its neuron number in senescence in humans. It was primarily related to the aging from psychological stress, the aging of bone, kidney and hypertension [34], and secondarily the aging of skin, stomach, and so on others requiring more investigation [34].

(3) Processes regulated by SDN-POA and sex hormones: The increment of adipose and aromatase in middle age converted more testosterone to estradiol by aromatase gradually, with male SDN-POA degenerated by such changes in sex hormones, so was speculated for the decay in female oocyte quality during menopause. This hypothalamic axis primarily controlled the aging of male and female reproductive system including hypothalamus [34], and secondarily controlled the aging of bone, thymus, hypertension, and so on others requiring further investigation[34].

(4) Specialties beyond hypothalamus: The skin aging primarily resulted from sunshine, oxygen and intracellular decrease in length of telomeres, which in

turn feedbacked to reduce both GH secretion and SCN neurons during aging via SWS. Besides, the aging of adipose tissue also seemed to be genetically programmed at the cellular level [37], which required further investigation.

The SCN, GH/IGF1 axis and nutritional functions are required for normal survival and repair of mammals while aging manifests as degeneration of these functions as shown above. Likewise, SDN-POA and sex hormones are required for normal reproduction of mammals while aging manifests as degeneration of these functions. In contrast, PVN, HPA axis and stress functions are required for normal activities and avoidance of mammals while aging manifests as maintenance of these functions. In this regard, aging manifests as the shift of balance among these three hypothalamic systems, with degeneration of SCN, GH/IGF1 axis, and nutritional system, as well as SDN-POA, and reproductive system, but maintenance of PVN, HPA axis, and stress system.

Conclusions

In this article, it is reviewed the recent progressions on peripheral mechanisms resulting in the degeneration of hypothalamic functions during aging in mammals. The neuron numbers decrease in both SCN and male SDN-POA during the process of aging, while the neuron number remains unchanged in PVN. The decrease in SWS resulting from continual skin aging causes both decrease in GH secretion and degeneration of SCN. The decreased ratio of testosterone/estradiol by increased adipose and aromatase causes the degeneration of male SDN-POA, while elevation of estradiol and FSH presumably causes the acceleration and precocity of oocytes in female menopause. The PVN responsible for stress response maintains its neuronal number unchanged during the aging in humans, resulting in many peripheral cellular and molecular changes of aging from chronic psychological stress, including the decrease in proteolytic clearance, change in length of telomere increase in DNA damage, alternation in immunological inflammation, and so on. Shift of balance occurs during aging among these three hypothalamic systems, with degeneration of SCN, GH/IGF1 axis, and nutritional system, as well as SDN-POA, and reproductive system, but maintenance of PVN, HPA axis, and stress system.

Authors' Contributions

The sole one author responsible for all of the article.

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Source of Funding

The author declares no financial support for this work.

Conflict of Interest Statement

The author declares no conflict of interest for this work.

References

- [1] Hofman MA. Lifespan Changes in the Human Hypothalamus. *Exp Gerontol.* 1997 Jul-Oct; 32(4-5): 559-575. Doi: 10.1016/s0531-5565(96)00162-3.
- [2] Aguilera G. HPA Axis Responsiveness to Stress: Implications for Healthy Aging. *Exp Gerontol.* 2011 Feb-Mar; 46(2-3): 90-95. Doi: 10.1016/j.exger.2010.08.023.
- [3] Zhou JN, Swaab DF. Activation and Degeneration during Aging: A Morphometric Study of the Human Hypothalamus. *Microscopy Research and Technique.* 1999 Jan; 44(1): 36-48. Doi: 10.1002/(SICI)1097-0029(19990101)44:1<36::AID-JEMT5>3.0.CO;2-F.
- [4] Hsieh YL, Hsu C, Yang SL, et al. Estradiol modulation of neuron loss in the medial division of medial preoptic nucleus in rats during aging. *Gerontology.* 1996 Jan; 42(1): 18-24. Doi: 10.1159/000213766.
- [5] Engelberth RC, Silva KD, Azevedo CV, et al. Morphological changes in the suprachiasmatic nucleus of aging female Marmosets (*Callithrix jacchus*). *Biomed Res Int.* 2014 Jun; 2014: 243825. Doi: 10.1155/2014/243825.
- [6] Panzica GC, García-Ojeda E, Viglietti-Panzica C, et al. Testosterone effects on vasotocinergic innervation of sexually dimorphic medial preoptic nucleus and lateral septum during aging in male Quail. *Brain Res.* 1996 Mar; 712(2): 190-198. Doi: 10.1016/0006-8993(95)01386-5.
- [7] Sattler FR. Growth hormone in the aging male. *Best Pract Res Clin Endocrinol Metab.* 2013 Aug; 27(4): 541-55. Doi: 10.1016/j.beem.2013.05.003.
- [8] Van Cauter E, Leproult R, Plat L. Age-related changes in slow wave sleep and REM sleep and relationship with growth hormone and cortisol levels in healthy men. *JAMA.* 2000 Aug; 284(7): 861-8. Doi: 10.1001/jama.284.7.861.
- [9] Kern W, Dodt C, Born J, et al. Changes in cortisol and growth hormone secretion during nocturnal sleep in the course of aging. *J Gerontol A Biol Sci Med Sci.* 1996 Jan; 51(1): M3-9. Doi: 10.1093/gerona/51a.1.m3.
- [10] Prior JC. Ovarian aging and the perimenopausal transition: The paradox of endogenous ovarian hyperstimulation. *Endocrine.* 2005 Apr; 26(3): 297-300. Doi: 10.1385/ENDO:26:3:297.
- [11] Reame NE, Kelche RP, Beitins IZ, et al. Age effects of follicle-stimulating hormone and pulsatile luteinizing hormone secretion across the menstrual cycle of premenopausal women. *J Clin Endocrinol Metab.* 1996 Apr; 81(4): 1512-1518. Doi: 10.1210/jc.81.4.1512.
- [12] Cai Z-J. The Regulation of Slow-Wave Sleep on Growth Hormone Secretion and Homeostatic Aging: A Pure Model in Man. *OALibJ.* 2024 Sep; 11: e2041. Doi: 10.4236/oalib.1112041.
- [13] Cai Z-J. A hypothetic aging pathway from skin to hypothalamic suprachiasmatic nucleus via slow wave sleep. *Sleep Sci.* 2016 Oct; 9: 212-215. Doi: 10.1016/j.slsci.2016.09.004.
- [14] Imokawa G. Recent advances in characterizing biological mechanisms underlying UV-induced wrinkles: a pivotal role of fibroblast-derived elastase. *Arch Dermatol Res.* 2008 Apr; 300(Suppl 1): S7-20. Doi: 10.1007/s00403-007-0798-x.
- [15] Zhuang Y, Hou H, Zhao X, et al. Effects of collagen and collagen hydrolysate from jellyfish (*Rhopilema esculentum*) on mice skin photoaging induced by UV irradiation. *J Food Sci.* 2009 Aug; 74(6): H183-188. Doi: 10.1111/j.1750-3841.2009.01236.x.
- [16] Kammeyer A, Luiten RM. Oxidation events and skin aging. *Ageing Res Rev.* 2015 May; 21: 16-29. Doi: 10.1016/j.arr.2015.01.001.
- [17] Rinnerthaler M, Bischof J, Streubel MK, et al. Oxidative stress in aging human skin. *Biomolecules.* 2015 Apr; 5(2): 545-589. Doi: 10.3390/biom5020545.
- [18] Buckingham EM, Klingelhutz AJ. The role of telomeres in the ageing of human skin. *Exp Dermatol.* 2011 Apr; 20(4): 297-302. Doi: 10.1111/j.1600-0625.2010.01242.x.
- [19] Siegl-Cachedenier I, Flores I, Klatt P, et al. Telomerase reverses epidermal hair follicle stem cell defects and loss of long-term survival associated with critically short telomeres. *J Cell Biol.* 2007 Oct; 179(2): 277-290. Doi: 10.1083/jcb.200704141.
- [20] Gavazzeni J, Wiens S, Fischer H. Age effects to negative arousal differ for self-report and electrodermal activity. *Psychophysiology.* 2008 Jan; 45(1): 148-151. Doi: 10.1111/j.1469-8986.2007.00596.x.
- [21] Powell DA, Milligan WL, Furchtgott E. Peripheral autonomic changes accompanying learning and reaction time performance in older people. *J Gerontol.* 1980 Jan; 35(1): 57-65. Doi: 10.1093/geronj/35.1.57.
- [22] Fusar-Poli P, Landi P, O'Connor C. Neurophysiological response to emotional faces with increasing intensity of fear: a skin conductance response study. *J Clin Neurosci.* 2009 Jul; 16(7): 981-982. Doi: 10.1016/j.jocn.2008.09.022.
- [23] Janka A, Duschek S. Self-reported stress and psychophysiological reactivity in paramedics. *Anxiety Stress Coping.* 2018 Jul; 31(4): 402-417. Doi: 10.1080/10615806.2018.1454739.
- [24] Morais P, Quaresma C, Vigário R, et al. Electrophysiological effects of mindfulness meditation in a concentration test. *Med Biol Eng Comput.* 2021 Apr; 59(4): 759-773. Doi: 10.1007/s11517-021-02332-y.
- [25] Cai Z-J. The functions of sleep: further analysis. *Physiol Behav.* 1991 Jul; 50: 53-60. Doi: 10.1111/10.1016/0031-9384(91)90497-C.

- [26] Cai Z-J. An integrative analysis to sleep functions. *Behav Brain Res.* 1995 Jul; 69, 187-194. Doi: 10.1016/0166-4328(95)00005-E.
- [27] Cai Z-J. Progressions of sleep, memory and depression applicable to psychoanalysis: A review. *Curr Psychiatr Rev.* 2016 Dec; 12, 240-245. Doi: 10.2174/1573400512666160610083505.
- [28] Ehlers CL, Kupfer DJ. Effects of age on delta and REM sleep parameters. *Electroencephalogr Clin Neurophysiol.* 1989 Feb; 72(2): 118-125. Doi: 10.1016/0013-4694(89)90172-7.
- [29] Espiritu JR. Aging-related Sleep Changes. *Clin Geriatr Med.* 2008 Feb; 24(1): 1-14. Doi: 10.1016/j.cger.2007.08.007.
- [30] Hirshkowitz M, Moore CA, Hamilton CR 3rd, et al. Polysomnography of adults and elderly: Sleep architecture, respiration, and leg movement. *J Clin Neurophysiol.* 1992 Jan; 9(1): 56-62. Doi: 10.1097/00004691-199201000-00006.
- [31] Nakagawa H, Okumura N. Coordinated regulation of circadian rhythms and homeostasis by the suprachiasmatic nucleus. *Proc Jpn Acad Ser B Phys Biol Sci* 2010 April; 86(4): 391-409. Doi: 10.2183/pjab.86.391.
- [32] Nijijima A, Nagai K, Nagai N, et al. Effects of light stimulation on the activity of the autonomic nerves in anesthetized rats. *Physiol Behav.* 1993 Sep; 54(3): 555-61. Doi: 10.1016/0031-9384(93)90249-f.
- [33] Cai Z-J. The peripheral hypotheses of hypothalamic aging. *OALibJ.* 2018 March; 5: e4445. Doi: 10.4236/oalib.1104445.
- [34] Cai Z-J. Hypothalamic aging and hormones. *Vitam Horm.* 2021 January; 115: 15-37. Doi: 10.1016/bs.vh.2020.12.002.
- [35] Sermondade N, Faure C, Fezeu L, et al. BMI in relation to sperm count: an updated systematic review and collaborative meta-analysis. *Hum Reprod Update.* 2013 May; 19(3): 221-231. Doi: 10.1093/humupd/dms050.
- [36] Cai Z-J. The spatial constraint requiring organogenetic termination: Supplemental to Haeckel and von Baer for development and evolution. *EJTAS.* 2024 Jun; 2(3): 504-516. Doi: 10.59324/ejtas.2024.2(3).39.
- [37] Cartwright MJ, Tchkonina T, Kirkland JL. Aging in adipocytes: Potential impact of inherent, depot-specific mechanisms. *Exp Gerontol.* 2007 Jun; 42(6): 463-471. Doi: 10.1016/j.exger.2007.03.003.
- [38] Cohen PG. Aromatase, adiposity, aging and disease. The hypogonadal-metabolic-atherogenic-disease and aging connection. *Med Hypotheses.* 2001 Jun; 56(6), 702-708. Doi: 10.1054/mehy.2000.1169.
- [39] Yamada K, Harada N. Expression of estrogen synthetase (P-450 aromatase) during adipose differentiation of 3T3-L1 cells. *Biochem Biophys Res Commun.* 1990 Jun; 169(2): 531-536. Doi: 10.1016/0006-291X(90)90363-R.
- [40] Vermeulen A, Kaufman JM, Goemaere S, et al. Estradiol in elderly men. *Aging Male.* 2002 Jun; 5(2): 98-102. Doi: 10.1080/tam.5.2.98.102.
- [41] Broekmans FJ, Knauff EA, te Velde ER, et al. Female reproductive ageing: current knowledge and future trends. *Trends Endocrinol Metab.* 2007 Mar; 18(2): 58-65. Doi: 10.1016/j.tem.2007.01.004.
- [42] Ye H, Zheng T, Li W, et al. (2017). Ovarian stem cell nests in reproduction and ovarian aging. *Cell Physiol Biochem.* 2017 Oct; 43(5): 1917-1925. Doi: 10.1159/000484114.
- [43] Koga H, Kaushik S, Cuervo AM. Protein homeostasis and aging: The importance of exquisite quality control. *Ageing Res Rev.* 2011 Apr; 10(2): 205-215. Doi: 10.1016/j.arr.2010.02.001.
- [44] Moreno-Villanueva M, Bürkle A. Molecular consequences of psychological stress in human aging. *Exp Gerontol.* 2015 Aug; 68: 39-42. Doi: 10.1016/j.exger.2014.12.003.

